

PLASTIC CTOD AS FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH CHARACTERISING PARAMETER UNDER VARIABLE AMPLITUDE LOADING BY USING DIC

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Although Paris' ΔK approach has been a useful tool for characterizing fatigue crack growth, it has not been without controversy due to its linear and elastic nature and therefore, its limitations in modelling some scenarios such as those involving large plasticity levels, among others. Thus, a potential way forward consists of developing new approaches based on parameters able to account for plasticity effects. Recent published works show promising results in terms of a more effective characterization of fatigue crack growth by the plastic component of the crack tip opening displacement range. This work shows how the plastic component of the crack tip opening displacement range is a suitable parameter to characterize fatigue crack growth rates under variable amplitude situations such as an overload. In this work, fatigue crack growth testing was performed in pure grade 2 Titanium Compact-Tension-specimens at low stress ratios for constant amplitude and variable amplitude loading scenarios. Plastic components of the crack tip opening displacement range for different crack lengths were measured using a high-resolution digital image correlation system. The obtained results show how the plastic component of the crack tip opening displacement range can perfectly model fatigue crack growth rates even for a phenomenon involving nonlinearity and plasticity such as the application of an overload on a specimen growing at constant amplitude loading.

Keywords: Fatigue crack growth, Plastic CTOD, Variable amplitude loading, Digital Image Correlation

INTRODUCTION

Paris' ΔK approach [1] along with Elber's crack closure correction [2,3] have been key over last years to characterize fatigue crack growth (FCG) rates and therefore contributing to a better design or assessment of in-service components under fatigue loadings. However, the linear and elastic nature of ΔK is in itself a limitation in modelling fatigue crack propagation since crack tip plasticity is an inherent phenomenon to fatigue cracks. Thus, the application of ΔK -based methodologies in modeling fatigue crack growth has sparked numerous controversies within this field [4–6]. A potential way forward lies in the use of parameters able to account for plasticity effects such as J or Crack Tip Opening Displacement (CTOD) rather than purely elastic parameters. Particularly, the plastic component of the CTOD range ($\Delta CTOD_p$) has proven to be a more suitable parameter in modelling fatigue crack growth rates. For example, plasticity-derived phenomena such as plasticity-induced crack closure and crack tip blunting, among others, are implicitly considered in that parameter and no correction is needed as with ΔK . Vasco-Olmo et al in [7] showed that the correlation between fatigue crack growth rates and $\Delta CTOD_p$ is linear, with the line slope remaining consistent across various stress ratios tested, solely dependent on the material. This implies that there

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is no stress ratio effects as is the case with K and therefore supposing a clearly advantage in modelling FCG rates. Moreover, the same trend was found in two different aluminium alloys (2024-T3 and 7050-T6) and in pure Grade 02 Titanium [8]. Proven the effectiveness of $\Delta CTOD_p$ for modelling FCG rates under constant amplitude loads in several materials and stress ratios, the aim of this study is to assess the suitability of this parameter in modeling fatigue crack growth under variable amplitude loading. Thus, in this work a FCG analysis using the $\Delta CTOD_p$ when a phenomenon involving high plasticity and non-linearity such as an overload occurs.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Fatigue crack growth testing was performed in commercially pure grade 02 Titanium CT specimens under constant amplitude loading at the frequency of 10 Hz (see Table 1 and 2 for mechanical properties and chemical composition, respectively and Figure 1a for specimen drawing).

TABLE 1 Mechanical properties of Grade 02 Titanium

Young's Modulus (GPa)	Yield Stress (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation at failure (%)	Poisson's ratio (-)
105	390	448	20	0.34

TABLE 2 Chemical composition (%wt) of Grade 02 Titanium

Fe	C	N	O	H	Ti
0.1	0.01	>0.01	0.12	0.002	Balance

The maximum applied load was 750 N and the stress ratio 0.1. A second test was performed at the same conditions but applying a 50% single overload (only one cycle overload) at a certain crack length (3 mm measured from the specimen notch). The two fatigue tests were performed at room temperature in a 25 kN load capacity servohydraulic machine (model MTS Landmark 370.02). The experimental measurement setup was comprising by two cameras, one in front of the specimen to acquire 2D-DIC images (model Redwood 65 MP) fitted to a macro lens (Laowa 60 mm F2.8 2X) and a second one (model AVT-Stingray 5MP) behind the specimen fitted to a macro-zoom lens (MLH-10X EO) to measure the crack length. The experimental setup is displayed in Figure 1b. A spatial resolution of 2 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pix}$ was achieved for DIC images and the DIC interest region was around 9×9 mm. DIC images were acquired for a whole loading cycle at different crack lengths and around 100 DIC images were captured at each crack length. For DIC measurements, the frequency was reduced to 0.01 Hz and an acquisition rate of one image per second was chosen. DIC processing was performed using commercial software VIC-2D provided by Correlated Solutions Inc. The employed DIC subset size was 41 with an overlap of 10 pixels by following the iDICs guideline recommendations [9].

FIGURE 1 A) Dimensions of CT specimen (millimeters) and B) Experimental setup

$\Delta CTOD_p$ CALCULATION FROM DIC DATA

In this section, the process to calculate $\Delta CTOD_p$ from DIC data is detailed. Figure 2a shows a DIC vertical displacement map at the maximum cycle load for a fatigue crack length of 3 mm. By taking different points at 0.1 mm from the crack along the crack flanks (see Figure 2b) for a whole loading cycle, $\Delta CTODs$ were calculated at each point as the difference between the displacements of the upper and lower points. By performing a sensitive analysis [8], the point of maximum $\Delta CTOD_p$ was chosen as suitable value.

FIGURE 2 (A) Vertical displacement map obtained by DIC and (B) detail image around the crack tip showing how CTOD values were calculated.

Figure 3 shows the crack tip opening displacement range against the applied load for a whole loading cycle. Note that Figure 3 shows different FCG phenomena such as crack closure and plasticity generation (cycle hysteresis).

FIGURE 3 Crack tip opening displacement against the applied load during a fatigue cycle showing how the ΔCTOD_p is calculated

The ΔCTOD_p is calculated by subtracting the elastic component of the crack tip opening displacement range (ΔCTOD_e) to total ΔCTOD [9]. Therefore, the first step is to determine the ΔCTOD_e . That value may be determined from the loading cycle data, however, points affected by crack closure at the beginning of the cycle complicates the analysis due to the definition of the opening/closure load. Hence, ΔCTOD_e was calculated using the unloading cycle data by performing linear least square fitting. Subsequently, that line slope was extrapolated to the loading cycle data as shown in Figure 3. Once the ΔCTOD_e is known, ΔCTOD_p is obtained as the difference between the CTOD and the fitted line at the maximum load of the cycle. This process was implemented in MATLAB software and it was applied to each analysed case.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows fatigue crack growth rates against the crack length for the two fatigue tests. Figure 4a for the constant amplitude loading test and Figure 4b for the 50% overload test. As shown in Figure 4a, FCG rates presents an expected trend for a constant amplitude loading test where those values are increasing as the fatigue crack grows. For the 50% overload tests, it is clearly visible in Figure 4b crack growth retardation because of the applied overload at a 3 mm crack length. As expected [10], a slight initial acceleration was found immediately after the application of the overload (point B) due to crack blunting which removes closure effects [10]. Following this, a retardation period was found. Each slight acceleration was expected since the acceleration occurred after overload application is usually significant for overloads higher than 50% [10]. The point of lowest crack growth rate (point C) was found at a crack length of 3.5 mm and after that, FCG rates begin to increase until reach a trend similar to that occurred before the application of the overload (point D).

FIGURE 4 Fatigue crack growth rates against $\Delta CTOD_p$ for A) constant amplitude loading test and B) 50% overload test.

Figure 5a shows fatigue crack growth rates against $\Delta CTOD_p$ values for the constant amplitude loading test. As shown and as previously reported by some authors [8,11], a linear relationship was found between fatigue crack growth rates and the $\Delta CTOD_p$. If a line equation as shown in equation 1 is fitted to those data, the slope of that curve can be obtained (see Figure 5).

$$\frac{da}{dN} = a \cdot \Delta CTOD_p \quad (1)$$

Figure 5b shows fatigue crack growth rates against $\Delta CTOD_p$ for the 50% overload test. In this Figure, the black and the white points indicate after and before the overload, respectively. It is worth noting that also for the overload test, it remains the linear relationship between FCG rates and $\Delta CTOD_p$. In fact, if the slope is obtained for this case, a similar value to the constant amplitude loading test was found as shown in Figure 5b. The obtained variation by comparing both slopes is around 6% which may be considered acceptable. That linear trend aims that $\Delta CTOD_p$ is a suitable parameter to model fatigue crack growth rates even when it occurs a phenomenon involving high-plasticity such as an overload. In addition, the good agreement between both slopes indicates that such constant may be a material intrinsic property since as reported in previous works; the curve slope also remains unchanged for different stress ratios [7].

FIGURE 5 Fatigue crack growth rates against $\Delta CTOD_p$ for A) constant amplitude loading test and B) 50% overload test.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a study of $\Delta CTOD_p$ as parameter governing fatigue crack growth has been performed in commercially pure Grade 02 Titanium samples using exclusively a non-contact technique such as digital image correlation for both constant amplitude loading and variable amplitude loading. The above exposed results show how the $\Delta CTOD_p$ can perfectly characterize fatigue crack growth rates even when there is a phenomenon involving high plasticity and non-linearity such as an overload. In addition, the observed linear relationship between FCG rates and $\Delta CTOD_p$ values gives a simple and effective rationalization of FCG rates. This work's results along with previous results by other authors shows that the $\Delta CTOD_p$ is a suitable parameter to model FCG rates since it removes effects of stress ratio and overloads in da/dN curves. The $\Delta CTOD_p$ approach also implies an uncertainty reduction in modelling FCG and therefore, this would result in a better design of elements under fatigue loads. Although this approach should be validated for more kind of materials, loading cases and different geometries, the exposed results show that the $\Delta CTOD_p$ is a promising parameter for modelling FCG rates in a broad range of cases.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

ΔK	Stress intensity factor range
FCG	Fatigue crack growth
J	J-Integral
CTOD	Crack tip opening displacement
$\Delta CTOD_p$	Plastic component of the crack tip opening displacement range
K	Stress intensity factor
DIC	Digital image correlation
$\Delta CTOD$	Crack tip opening displacement range
$\Delta CTOD_e$	Elastic component of the crack tip opening displacement range
da/dN	Fatigue crack growth rate
α	Coefficient of fatigue crack growth rate equation

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